

Inventory Model for Deteriorating Item with Partial Prepayment and Trade Credit under Variable Holding Cost and Partial Backlogging

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Abstract- This article proposes an inventory model for deteriorating item with partial backlogging and lost sales under a situation where the supplier requests a partial prepayment at the time of placing the order prior to the beginning of the selling season and offers a trade credit period for remaining due to his/her retailer. To pay the supplier for the advance payment, the retailer gets a loan from a bank with the condition that he/she will be paid at the end of business period with interest. Holding cost is assumed to be an increasing function of time. The validation of the proposed model is demonstrated through a numerical example. The results indicate that the inventory model provides a powerful tool to the retailers under real-world situations.

Keywords- *Deteriorating items, selling price dependent demand, partial backlogging, prepayment and trade credit.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The classical EOQ framework for a supply chain system assumes that purchasing and order cost are paid once an order is placed by the retailer. In reality, sometimes a supplier prefers the buyer to pay before the date of delivery as a prepayment (i.e. advance payment) to prevent cancellation of the orders. Again, some suppliers offer their buyers a delayed payment to stimulate their sales. In this inventory model, we use the above two realistic incentive schemes, viz. Prepayment and trade credit.

Trade credit financing for inventory model was first introduced by Haley and Higgins [4] where they studied the relationship between inventory policy and credit policy. Goyal [3] derived an EOQ model under trade credit policy. Deterioration is a process that decreases usefulness and utility of a product from its original state. Ghare and Schrader [2] first introduced deterioration of products into an EOQ model. Aggarwal and Jaggi [1] modified Goyal's model by adding deterioration to the model. Goyal's model was further extended by Jamal et al. [5] considering shortage under a permissible delay in payment. Maiti et al. [6] introduced an inventory model with stochastic lead-time and price dependent demand incorporating advance payment. Taleizadeh et al. [10] developed an EOQ problem under partial delayed payment. Tai et al. [9] presented an inventory model to formulate the process in which deteriorating products were sold together with serviceable products. Singh and Singh [8] considered an optimal inventory policy for deteriorating items with stock level and selling price dependent demand under the permissible delay in payments. Singh and Kumar [7] presented optimal ordering and replenishment policies for deteriorating items having a fixed expiry date with price and credit period sensitive demand under a permissible credit period. Taleizadeh et al. [11] investigated the impact of an inspection policy on the optimality of the solution under hybrid payment strategies for the deteriorating products. They propose an inventory model with disparate inventory ordering policies under a situation where a portion of serviceable products and a portion of deteriorating products are sold together to consumers (i.e. mixed sales).

In most of the previous work, holding cost has been considered as constant under trade credit policy. In this model, we try to fill up this lacuna by considering retailer's payment decisions for selling price-dependent demand with variable holding cost under partial advance payment and trade credit. Here, the retailer gets a loan from a financier to pay the supplier for the advance payment. Then, the revenue of sale is used to pay remaining due at the end of the trade credit period and to pay back the loan at the end of the replenishment cycle.

II. ASSUMPTIONS AND NOTATIONS

The following notations and assumptions are introduced to define the inventory model for deteriorating item with partial prepayment and trade credit.

2.1 Notations

The following notations are used to develop the proposed inventory model.

Notation	Description
a, b	: Demand parameters
h_1, h_2	: Holding cost parameters
θ	: Deterioration parameter with $0 \leq \theta \ll 1$
α	: Fraction of purchasing and ordering cost must be paid as prepayment
η	: Backlogging parameter with $0 \leq \eta \leq 1$
p	: Purchasing cost per unit
s	: Selling price per unit with $s \geq p$
O	: Ordering cost per order
d	: Deterioration cost per unit per unit time
k	: Shortage cost per unit per unit time
L	: Lost sales cost per unit per unit time
$I(t)$: Inventory level at any time t
Q_1	: Initial stock level at $t = 0$
Q_2	: Maximum backordered quantity during stock out period
Q	: Order quantity per replenishment cycle
v	: Point of time at which inventory level vanishes
T	: The length of replenishment cycle
I_c	: Rate of interest charged by the bank to the retailer
I_e	: Rate of interest given by the bank to the retailer ($I_e < I_c$)
l	: The prepayment period offered by the supplier to the retailer
M	: The trade-credit period offered by the supplier to the retailer

2.2 Assumptions

To develop the proposed inventory model, the following assumptions are made.

1. There is a single supplier and single retailer and they deal with a single item.
2. The item considered here is deteriorating in nature and there is no repair or replacement of the deteriorated units during the cycle.
3. The retailer starts selling the items as soon as he/she receives it.
4. The consumer demand rate is assumed to be deterministic and a linear function of retailer's selling price of the item. For simplicity, the demand rate $D(s)$ is taken as $D(s) = a - bs$, where $a > 0$ stands for the initial demand and $b > 0$.
5. Shortages are allowed and partially backlogged with a constant rate η during the stock out situation.
6. Holding cost $h(t)$ per item per unit time is assumed to be an increasing function of time and considered as $h(t) = h_1 + h_2 t$, where $h_1, h_2 \geq 0$.
7. The supplier demands his/her retailer to prepay ordering cost and a fraction α of the total purchasing cost, before the time of delivery of the item and provides a fixed credit period M to settle the remaining dues to the retailer. To pay the supplier for the advance payment, the retailer gets a loan from a bank with the condition that he/she will be paid at the end of business period T with interest.

III. FORMULATION OF MATHEMATICAL INVENTORY MODEL

Consider a situation where a supplier demands his/her retailer to prepay order cost and a fraction α of the total purchasing cost when an order is placed, as the prepayment at time l before the delivery of the ordered quantity. To pay the supplier for the advance payment, the retailer gets a loan from a bank with the condition that he/she will be paid at the end of business period T with interest. The supplier also provides a fixed credit period M to settle the remaining dues to the retailer. Figure.1 depicts the behavior of the inventory level over time. In this model, the retailer places an order and pays ordering cost and a fraction α of total purchasing cost at time l before the delivery of the ordered quantity. The retailer receives the item at initial time $t = 0$. During the time interval $[0, v]$, the inventory level depletes as a result of cumulative effects of demand and deterioration until it reduces to zero. At $t = v$ the inventory level becomes zero and there after shortages occur. During the time interval $[v, T]$, the inventory level is depends only demand and unsatisfied demand is backlogged partially. At $t = T$ the retailer receive the new lot and the process goes on.

Therefore, the inventory level at any instant of time t is described by the following differential equations

$$\frac{dI(t)}{dt} = -\theta I(t) - D(s), \quad 0 \leq t \leq v \tag{1}$$

$$\frac{dI(t)}{dt} = -\eta D(s), \quad v \leq t \leq T \tag{2}$$

with the boundary condition $I(v) = 0$

The solutions of the above differential equations are given by

$$I(t) = (a - bs) \left\{ (v - t) + \frac{\theta}{2} (v - t)^2 \right\}, \quad 0 \leq t \leq v \tag{3}$$

$$I(t) = -(a - bs)(t - v), \quad v \leq t \leq T \tag{4}$$

With the help of equation (3) and (4), we get

Fig.1: The graphical representation of behavior of the inventory level over time

$$\text{The maximum positive inventory} = Q_1 = I(0) = (a - bs) \left\{ v + \frac{\theta}{2} v^2 \right\} \tag{5}$$

$$\text{The maximum backordered quantity} = Q_2 = -I(T) = \eta(a - bs)(T - v) \tag{6}$$

$$\text{Hence, the order quantity per cycle is given by } Q = Q_1 + Q_2 = (a - bs) \left\{ v + \frac{\theta}{2} v^2 + \eta(T - v) \right\} \tag{7}$$

The total profit of the retailer per unit time per cycle is composed of ordering cost, purchasing cost, sales revenue, deterioration cost, holding cost, shortage cost, lost sales cost, interest charged and interest earned. These components are evaluated as follows:

a) **Ordering Cost:** The ordering cost per unit time per cycle is given by $OC = \frac{O}{T}$ (8)

b) **Purchasing Cost:** The purchasing cost per unit time per cycle is given by $PC = \frac{pQ}{T} = \frac{p(a-bs)}{T} \left\{ v + \frac{\theta}{2}v^2 + \eta(T-v) \right\}$ (9)

c) **Sales Revenue:** Since Q_2 is the total backordered quantity per cycle, the total sales revenue per unit time per cycle is given by $SR = \frac{s}{T} \left\{ \int_0^v D(s)dt + Q_2 \right\} = \frac{s(a-bs)}{T} \{ (1-\eta)v + \eta T \}$ (10)

d) **Holding Cost:** Inventory holding cost per unit time per cycle is given by $HC = \int_0^v (h_1 + h_2t) I(t) dt$
 $HC = \frac{(a-bs)}{T} \left\{ h_1 \left(\frac{v^2}{2} + \frac{\theta}{6}v^3 \right) + h_2 \left(\frac{v^3}{6} + \frac{\theta}{24}v^4 \right) \right\}$ (11)

e) **Deterioration Cost:** The cost associated with the deteriorated units is calculated as $DC = \frac{d}{T} \left\{ Q_1 - \int_0^v D(s)dt \right\} = \frac{d(a-bs)}{T} \left(\theta \frac{v^2}{2} \right)$ (12)

f) **Shortage Cost:** The shortage cost per unit time per cycle is given by $SC = \frac{k}{T} \int_v^T \{-I(t)\} dt = \frac{k(a-bs)}{2T} (T-v)^2$ (13)

g) **Lost Sales Cost:** During the stock-out period, all the customers do not wait up to next arrival. Some customers purchase from any other place. So the cost associated with the lost sales can be calculated as $LSC = \frac{L}{T} \int_v^T (1-\eta)D(s)dt = \frac{L(a-bs)}{T} (1-\eta)(T-v)$ (14)

The partial advance payment of each replenishment cycle consists of order cost and a fraction α of the purchase cost of the order quantity. The partial advance payment is made at the time of placing the order before the beginning of each selling season. It is borrowed from the financial institution like banks with the condition that it will be paid at the end of each replenishment cycle T with interest at the rate I_c . The total interest charged by the financial institution on it per unit time per cycle is calculated as

$$IC = \frac{I_c}{T} \{ (O + \alpha pQ)(T+l) \} = \frac{I_c(T+l)}{T} \left[O + \alpha p(a-bs) \left\{ v + \frac{\theta}{2}v^2 + \eta(T-v) \right\} \right]$$
 (15)

The retailer starts selling his items from the beginning of the selling season. The sales revenue is invested in the banks to earn interest at the rate I_e . The supplier also provides a fixed credit period M to settle the remaining dues to the retailer. The remaining dues are made by the retailer under two different cases as follow:

Case 1: When the credit period is less than equal to the selling period i.e. $M \leq v$.

Case 2: When the credit period is greater than the selling period i.e. $v < M \leq T$.

3.1 Case 1: $M \leq v$

Fig.2: When $M \leq v$

In this case, the credit period $[0, M]$ provided by the supplier is less than equal to the selling period $[0, v]$. Therefore, the sale revenue in this period is calculated as

$$SR_1[0, M] = s \int_0^M D(s) dt = s(a - bs)M \tag{16}$$

And the interest earned on this sale revenue in this credit period is calculated as

$$IE_1[0, M] = sI_e \int_0^M D(s) t dt = \frac{I_e}{2} s(a - bs)M^2 \tag{17}$$

Based on the difference in the total amount generated by sales revenue and earned interest on this sales revenue during the time interval $[0, M]$ and the remaining dues $(1 - \alpha)pQ$, two different subcases may arise:-

Subcase 1.1: When $SR_1[0, M] + IE_1[0, M] \geq (1 - \alpha)pQ$

Subcase 1.2: When $SR_1[0, M] + IE_1[0, M] < (1 - \alpha)pQ$

3.1.1 Subcase 1.1: When $SR_1[0, M] + IE_1[0, M] \geq (1 - \alpha)pQ$

In this subcase, the total interest earned by the retailer per unit time per cycle is given by

$$IE_{1.1} = \frac{I_e}{T} \left[(T - M) \left\{ SR_1[0, M] + IE_1[0, M] - (1 - \alpha)pQ \right\} + s \int_M^v D(s) t dt + (T - v) s \int_M^v D(s) dt \right]$$

$$IE_{1.1} = \frac{I_e(a - bs)}{T} \left[(T - M) \left\{ sM + \frac{I_e}{2} sM^2 - (1 - \alpha)p \left\{ v + \frac{\theta}{2} v^2 + \eta(T - v) \right\} \right\} + \frac{1}{2} s(v - M)(2T - v + M) \right] \tag{18}$$

In this subcase, the total interest charged to the retailer per unit time per cycle is given by

$$IC_{1.1} = IC = \frac{I_c(T + l)}{T} \left[O + \alpha p(a - bs) \left\{ v + \frac{\theta}{2} v^2 + \eta(T - v) \right\} \right] \tag{19}$$

Hence, the total profit of the retailer per unit time per cycle is given by

$$Z_{1.1} = \{ (SR + IE_{1.1}) - (OC + PC + HC + DC + SC + LSC + IC_{1.1}) \} \tag{20}$$

3.1.2 Subcase 1.2: When $SR_1[0, M] + IE_1[0, M] < (1 - \alpha)pQ$

In this subcase, the total interest earned by the retailer per unit time per cycle is given by

$$IE_{1.2} = \frac{I_e}{T} \left[s \int_M^v D(s) dt + (T-v) s \int_M^v D(s) dt \right] = \frac{I_e(a-bs)}{2T} \{s(v-M)(2T-v+M)\} \tag{21}$$

In this subcase, the total interest charged to the retailer per unit time per cycle is given by

$$IC_{1.2} = IC + \frac{I_c(T-M)}{T} \{ (1-\alpha)pQ - SR_1[0, M] - IE_1[0, M] \}$$

$$IC_{1.2} = \frac{I_c}{T} \left[\begin{aligned} & (T+l) \left\{ O + \alpha p(a-bs) \left\{ v + \frac{\theta}{2} v^2 + \eta(T-v) \right\} \right\} \\ & + (T-M)(a-bs) \left\{ \begin{aligned} & (1-\alpha)p \left\{ v + \frac{\theta}{2} v^2 + \eta(T-v) \right\} \\ & - \frac{s}{2} (2M + I_e M^2) \end{aligned} \right\} \end{aligned} \right] \tag{22}$$

Hence, the total profit of the retailer per unit time per cycle is given by

$$Z_{1.2} = \{ (SR + IE_{1.2}) - (OC + PC + HC + DC + SC + LSC + IC_{1.2}) \} \tag{23}$$

3.2 Case 2: $v < M \leq T$

In this case, the credit period $[0, M]$ provided by the supplier is greater than to the selling period $[0, v]$. Therefore, the sale revenue in this period is calculated as

$$SR[0, M] = s \int_0^v D(s) dt = s(a-bs)v \tag{24}$$

And the interest earned on this sale revenue in this credit period is calculated as

$$IE[0, M] = sI_e \left\{ \int_0^v D(s) t dt + (M-v) \int_0^v D(s) dt \right\} = \frac{I_e}{2} s(a-bs)(2vM - v^2) \tag{25}$$

Fig.3: When $v < M \leq T$

In this case, the retailer has enough money in his/her account to settle the account at the end of the credit period. After paying the remaining dues, amount in the interests bearing account of the retailer is given by

$$U = SR[0, M] + IE[0, M] - (1-\alpha)pQ$$

$$U = (a-bs) \left[sv + \frac{I_e}{2} s(2vM - v^2) - (1-\alpha)p \left\{ v + \frac{\theta}{2} v^2 + \eta(T-v) \right\} \right] \tag{26}$$

In this case, the total interest earned by the retailer per unit time per cycle is given by

$$IE_2 = \frac{I_e}{T}(T - M)U = \frac{I_e(a - bs)}{T}(T - M) \left[sv + \frac{I_e}{2}s(2vM - v^2) - (1 - \alpha)p \left\{ v + \frac{\theta}{2}v^2 + \eta(T - v) \right\} \right] \quad (27)$$

In this case, the total interest charged to the retailer per unit time per cycle is given by

$$IC_2 = IC = \frac{I_c(T + l)}{T} \left[O + \alpha p(a - bs) \left\{ v + \frac{\theta}{2}v^2 + \eta(T - v) \right\} \right] \quad (28)$$

Hence, the total profit of the retailer per unit time per cycle is given by

$$Z_2 = \{(SR + IE_2) - (OC + PC + HC + DC + SC + LSC + IC_2)\} \quad (29)$$

Our goal is to maximize the total profit of the retailer per unit time with respect to the critical time v and the replenishment cycle time T . The nonlinearity of the profit functions does not allow obtaining the closed form solution. We analyze the model with numerical data for the inventory parameters in the next section.

IV. NUMERICAL AND SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS OF THE MATHEMATICAL INVENTORY MODEL

In this section, the numerical analysis of the retailer’s profit function for this model is presented to obtain the optimal value of the decision variable. We also study the sensitivity analysis on the optimal value of the decision variable with respect to some important parameters in appropriate units. The following input data is used in proper units to find out the optimal value of the decision variable:

$$a = 1000, b = 0.50, h_1 = 10, h_2 = 2.00, \theta = 0.01, \alpha = 0.30, \eta = 0.6, p = 500, s = 800,$$

$$O = 5000, d = 25, k = 15, L = 20, I_e = 7.00, I_c = 10.00, l = 2, M = 5.$$

By using MATHEMATICA 11.2, we have the following optimal value of the decision variable in appropriate units:

$$v = 27.7055, T = 39.7532 \text{ and } Z = 2.38751 \times 10^8.$$

Fig. 4: Concavity of the Retailer's Profit Function

Using the same data, we present a sensitivity analysis of the optimal solution with respect to relevant and important parameters such as α, η, θ, L and M . The computational results of this analysis are shown in Table 1.

Table 1				
Parameter		Decision Variable		
		v	T	Z
α	0.10	30.7573	42.1111	2.49331×10^8
	0.30	27.7055	39.7532	2.38751×10^8
	0.50	25.1249	37.2402	2.28880×10^8
η	0.40	26.0989	46.6664	2.45285×10^8
	0.60	27.7055	39.7532	2.38751×10^8
	0.80	29.5630	36.0624	2.35089×10^8
θ	0.01	27.7055	39.7532	2.38751×10^8
	0.02	22.0877	36.5029	2.31957×10^8
	0.03	18.7212	34.9410	2.27366×10^8
M	3	16.4990	20.1678	8.34437×10^7
	5	27.7055	39.7532	2.38751×10^8
	7	37.6846	62.0264	4.75637×10^8

The sensitivity analysis reveals that:

1. An increase (decrease) in the fraction of advance payment causes decreases (increases) in a total profit of the retailer.
2. An increase (decrease) in the backlogging rate causes decreases (increases) in a total profit of the retailer.
3. An increase (decrease) in the deteriorating rate causes decreases (increases) in a total profit of the retailer.
4. An increase (decrease) in trade-credit period causes the increases (decreases) in a total profit of the retailer.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE RESEARCH

Advance payment has been widely used in the real world; however, its influences on inventory modeling have rarely been addressed. In this paper, we derive the buyer’s optimal inventory policy when payment is required to pay before delivery. We have developed an inventory model for the retailer with partial backordering and lost sales when the supplier demands his/her retailer a partial prepayment before delivery, and the product gradually deteriorates. The supplier also grants a permissible delay in payment to the remaining unpaid balance. Then, we have mathematically demonstrated that the retailer’s profit function is concave on decision variables: the replenishment cycle time and the point of time at which inventory level vanishes. Consequently, the exploration for the global solution has been simplified to find the unique local maximum.

The proposed model can be extended in several ways. The model could expand from a single player to multi-player model for both the retailer and the supplier. In addition, we can generalize the demand pattern to a demand function of time, advertising and product quality.

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